

EFFECT OF OIL PRICE VOLATILITY ON PERSISTENT PETROL SHORTAGES IN THE OIL PRODUCING ECONOMY: EVIDENCE FROM POST-COLONIAL NIGERIA

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Abstract

This part of the research also examines the effect of oil price volatility, which is an inherent characteristic of the international oil market. Following this, the author argues that oil price volatility in the international market contributes to the lingering crisis of Nigeria's major petroleum exporting country, namely, petrol shortages. The article explained the international oil market's character and Nigeria's dependence on it for the import of refined oil. Under this sub-theme, I identified three major forces that influence the volatile posture of the oil market and how these forces are conditioned/determined to account for persistent product scarcity in Nigeria. The article benefits from a collection of various data, including interviews, archival materials, newspaper articles, and peer-reviewed journal articles, to analyze this important element that has challenged the domestic economy's adequate supply of petrol and contributed to the perennial scarcity of petrol.

Keywords: *Petrol Shortages, Oil Producing Economy, Oil Price Volatility, International Oil Market*

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria is a reputable member of the OPEC.¹ Unfortunately, the country has been challenged by persistent petrol shortages that have continued to inhibit socio-economic and political activities for most of its post-independence life. Therefore, this article aims to explain the paradox in which a country with some of the world's largest oil reserves continues to experience chronic and perennial shortages of petrol. I argue that Nigeria is subjected to the vagaries of the international oil market because it is an exporter of crude oil and an importer of refined oil, a factor that has no doubt contributed to the challenges of petrol shortages within its domestic economy. To explain how Nigeria became hooked in the international oil market, leading to persistent petrol shortages, I analyzed the volatile character of the international market for oil and Nigeria's overdependence on it for the sale of crude oil and as an avenue to buy refined oil to meet increasing demand.

¹Wagner and Heather Lehr Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries Infobase Publishing, 2009.

INTERNATIONAL OIL MARKET

According to Hamilton, the relative importance of oil to the economy of almost all countries worldwide led to an increase in the volume of oil exports to the international market.² A United Nations Report in 2008 estimated that approximately \$4 billion is expended daily for the purchase of both refined and crude oil in the international market.³ In the same report, the total automobile exports stood at \$1.5 billion per day, while iron and steel exports accounted for only \$1 billion per day.⁴ Economists have long argued that almost all countries are remarkably susceptible to changes in the market for oil.⁵ Although the effect of changes in the international market does not spare any country, including producing and consuming states, it has a greater implication for countries such as Nigeria that “depend on the international market” for the import of refined petrol.⁶ It is within this understanding of Nigeria as an exporter of crude oil and an importer of refined petrol that this section would focus on. In the following, the character of the international market in which Nigeria is both a seller and a buyer of oil and how this dual attribute contributes to the menace of petrol shortages within its domestic market are examined.

The international market for oil is occupied by about 50 states that are producers, with more than half of the oil produced being exported for rent.⁷ Except for the recent modest search for alternative sources of energy, which in the long run may have some significant impact on the international oil market by changing its geo-politics, the leading exporters of crude oil are Middle Eastern states, the Russian Federation, and the African states of Nigeria, Angola, and Libya, among others.⁸ China, European countries, the United States, India, and Japan are known oil importers.⁹ Like automobiles, oil is categorized into grades, with each competing for space within a highly “aggressive international market environment.”¹⁰

However, approximately 50 years ago, the seven most powerful oil transnational corporations remotely controlled the international oil market. However,¹¹ since the establishment of the OPEC in 1960, state-owned corporations have challenged the dominant position of these transnationals.¹² Before Nigeria joined

²Hamilton, James D. "Oil and the macroeconomy since World War II." *Journal of political economy* 91, no. 2 (1983): 228-248.

³Comtrade, U. N. "United Nations commodity trade statistics database." URL: <http://comtrade.un.org> (2008) available at <http://comtrade.un.org/pb/> accessed 12/November/2018).

⁴Ibid., 4

⁵Sandalow, David. "Ending oil dependence." *Washington: The Brookings Institution* (2007).

⁶Sanusi, Lamido Sanusi. "Growth prospects for the Nigerian economy." *Convocation Lecture* (2010).

⁷BP, p.l.c. *BP Statistical Review of World Energy* 2008.

⁸Kheiravar, Khaled H., C-YC Lin Lawell, James B. Bushnell, Amy Myers Jaffe, and Erich J. Muehlegger. *Structural econometric model of the dynamic game between petroleum producers in the world petroleum market* Working paper, Cornell University, 2017.

⁹Pirog, Robert L. "The role of national oil companies in the international oil market." Congressional Research Service, Library of Congress, 2007.

¹⁰Bentzen, Jan. "Does OPEC influence crude oil prices? Testing for co-movements and causality between regional crude oil prices." *Applied Economics* 39, no. 11 (2007): 1375-1385.

¹¹Esso, British Petroleum, Shell, Gulf, Texaco, Standard Oil (California), Mobil, and Compagnie Française des Pétroles. Through various mergers and consolidation, the eight have been reduced to five: ExxonMobil, BP, Shell, Chevron, and Total.

¹²Terzian, Pierre. OPEC. London: Zed Books; Totowa, NJ, USA: Distributor, Biblio Distribution Center, 1985.

the Organization of the Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC) in the 1970s, the dominant transnational corporations, otherwise known as the “seven sisters,” were arguably the most significant stakeholders in the oil sector, accounting for almost 90% of the total oil output from Nigeria.¹³ However, after the nationalists’ motivated transition to state control of the oil sector, inspired by OPEC rules, the NNPC assumed control, at least according to the legal framework governing the industry.¹⁴ At the international level, the economic space dominated by corporations has narrowed from 90% to a negligible 12% in the 1970s courtesy of OPEC’s membership conditions, which mandate producers to control the sector.¹⁵

As a result of the restructuring of the 1970s, oil production to feed the international oil market is now dominated by major oil producers through state-owned companies.¹⁶ These national oil companies supply more than 50% of the crude oil in the international market while controlling about 70% of proven oil reserves.¹⁷ Their activities are subject to different national governing frameworks with no formal international rules. However, transnational corporations still maintain dominance in refining petroleum for the international market. However, most of the OPEC members, including Nigeria, are mandated to have firm control of the downstream sector. However, due to “politics and corruption,”¹⁸ the refineries in Nigeria have not been working at maximum capacity, making the country rely on the “international market for both the sale of crude oil and buying of refined oil including petrol.”¹⁹ Of the 20 largest oil companies in the world, nine are officially attached to OPEC, including Nigeria’s state-owned corporation, Nigeria National Petroleum Corporation Limited (NNPCL).²⁰

Volatility in Oil Prices in the International Market

The subject of oil price volatility has long been debated.²¹ While many scholars still differ regarding the causes of oil price volatility, a near consensus seems to exist on the volatile posture of oil prices in the international market.²² As noted above, both crude and refined oil are involved. “But these differences do not really count in the peculiar case of Nigeria considering that it produces and sells crude at the international market and simultaneously depends on the international market for refined petroleum products,” argues Marhino.²³ To understand the causal factors of volatility in oil prices, it is important to first explain volatility as a concept. This is essential because of the misconceptions surrounding its

¹³Adelman, M. A. "The World Petroleum Market." Baltimore and London." (1972).

¹⁴Omorogbe, Yinka. "Oil and gas law in Nigeria." *Lagos, Nigeria: Malthouse Press Limited* (2001).

¹⁵Weekly, Petroleum Intelligence. "PIW ranks the world’s top 50 oil companies." *Energy Intelligence Group*, 2008.

¹⁶Cuervo, Luis E. "OPEC from the Myth to Reality." *Hous. J. Int’l L.* 30 (2007): 433.

¹⁷ Alhajji, Anas F., and David Huettner. "OPEC and world crude oil markets from 1973 to 1994: cartel, oligopoly, or competitive?" *The Energy Journal* (2000): 31-60.

¹⁸Interview with Akin Iwayemi (aged 64) on May 23, 2019.

¹⁹ Iwayemi, Akin, and Babajide Fowowe. "Impact of oil price shocks on selected macroeconomic variables in Nigeria." *Energy policy* 39, no. 2 (2011): 603-612. p. 606.

²⁰*Petroleum Intelligence Weekly*, December 4, 2008.

²¹Ferderer, J. Peter. "Oil price volatility and the macroeconomy." *Journal of macroeconomics* 18, no. 1 (1996): 1-26.

²²Regnier, Eva. "Oil and energy price volatility." *Energy economics* 29, no. 3 (2007): 405-427.

²³Interview with Festus Marhino (aged 87) on May 25, 2019. He is the pioneer head of Nigeria’s NNPC.

meaning. It has been perceived as a persistent increase in the market “price of commodities.”²⁴ This school of thought does not regard downward trends in the price of commodities as volatility. Based on its limited outlook, Ayadi argues that this reduces the basis on which the notion of volatility is used.²⁵ Others see volatility from a chaotic angle based on the market’s unpredictability.²⁶ While unpredictability is a major characteristic of volatility, it cannot be equated with volatility. Consequently, for the purposes of this study, Shiller’s definition of volatility as both the increase and decrease in the price of commodities is adopted.²⁷ Measures the degree to which the prices of commodities vary in the market. Influenced by Shiller’s conceptualization, Radchenko observed the extent of volatility in oil prices, describing extreme upward trends as “high volatility” and extreme downward trends as “low volatility.”²⁸

In normal circumstances, what economists have described as “efficient market conditions,”²⁹ the prices of commodities revolve around familiar prevailing and mostly predictable conditions, usually referred to as “demand and supply forces.”³⁰ Therefore, even before changes in market outlooks come to reality, they must have been anticipated.” However, when these changes occur frequently with virulent repercussions, economists regard such scenarios as “high volatility.”³¹ It is within this attribute of high volatility that the price of oil in the international market can be understood.” While incidences of high volatility are celebrated by oil-producing countries, it has negative consequences for oil-importing countries because they spend more for the same quantity, sometimes leading to “inflation.”³² Contradictorily, Nigeria is an oil exporter that can gain more during periods of high volatility. However, since it depends on the international market for the bulk of its refined oil, it tends to use its gains to buy refined petrol at “higher prices like oil importers.”³³

²⁴Oriakhi, D. E., and Iyoha Daniel Osaze. "Oil price volatility and its consequences on the growth of the Nigerian economy: An examination (1970-2010)." *Asian economic and financial review* 3, no. 5 (2013): 683.

²⁵Ayadi, O. Felix. "Oil price fluctuations and the Nigerian economy." *OPEC review* 29, no. 3 (2005): 199-217.

²⁶ Chavas, Jean-Paul, and Matthew T. Holt. "Market instability and nonlinear dynamics." *American Journal of Agricultural Economics* 75, no. 1 (1993): 113-120.

²⁷Shiller, R. J. *Market Volatility*. MIT Press, 1992.

²⁸ Radchenko, Stanislav. "Oil price volatility and the asymmetric response of gasoline prices to oil price increases and decreases." *Energy economics* 27, no. 5 (2005): 708-730.

²⁹ Jensen, Michael C. "Some anomalous evidence regarding market efficiency." *Journal of financial economics* 6, no. 2/3 (1978): 95-101.

³⁰ Krichene, Noureddine. "World crude oil and natural gas: a demand and supply model." *Energy economics* 24, no. 6 (2002): 557-576.

³¹ Gençay, Ramazan, Faruk Selçuk, and Abdurrahman Ulugülyağci. "High volatility, thick tails and extreme value theory in value-at-risk estimation." *Insurance: Mathematics and Economics* 33, no. 2 (2003): 337-356.

³²Judson, Ruth, and Athanasios Orphanides. "Inflation, Volatility and Growth." *international Finance* 2, no. 1 (1999): 117-138.

³³Ehinomen, Christopher, and Adepoju Adeleke. "An assessment of the distribution of petroleum products in Nigeria." *E3 Journal of Business Management and Economics* 3, no. 6 (2012): 232-241.

However, the question that readily comes to mind is what makes oil prices susceptible to volatility, leading to extremes, both low and high. Scholars, including McNally,³⁴ Kaufmann,³⁵ and Adelman, have³⁶ identified various basic causal factors, including geopolitical developments, the OPEC system of production, demand and supply, appreciation of the U.S. dollar, and non-OPEC members, as the major forces inducing volatility. However, a careful study of the empirical data shows that only three of the abovementioned factors have had an enormous influence on Nigeria's petrol shortage menace. These factors include geopolitical developments, the OPEC system of production, and exchange rate fluctuations. Following from these factors, I explained how these factors have engendered oil shortages in Nigeria using many sources without excluding empirical data.

Geo-political Developments

The relationship between oil and politics is so intrinsic that any political disruption or tension within the international system would have remarkable implications on the price, leading to volatility.³⁷ Disruptions occasioned by political tensions almost always have implications on the international market price of both crude and refined oil. Political tensions emanating from oil-producing countries or sources of imports have always had a significant effect on the prices of oil within the broader international oil market, depending on the nature of the oil industry's organization in the domestic economy of oil-producing countries.³⁸ Following from the analogy provided above, I explained chronologically how two political tensions around the world, especially in the Middle East, affected oil prices with consequences on the prices of petrol in Nigeria.

The First Oil Shock

Beginning with the Yom Kippur War (October 1973) involving Israel and Middle Eastern states such as Syria and Egypt, tensions have been shown to have remarkable implications on oil prices.³⁹ The conflict began to have a serious effect on the price of oil when the frontline decision-makers of the Organization of Arab Petroleum Exporting Countries (OAPEC) imposed an oil embargo on Western nations considered core supporters of the Israeli course.⁴⁰ The nations affected by the oil embargo included "Canada, Japan, the Netherlands, the United Kingdom, and the United States."⁴¹ However, following intelligent reports of

³⁴McNally, Robert. *Crude Volatility: The History and Future of Oil Prices in Boom and Bust* Columbia University Press, 2017.

³⁵ Kaufmann, Robert K., and Cheryl Laskowski. "Causes for an asymmetric relation between the price of crude oil and refined petroleum products." *Energy Policy* 33, no. 12 (2005): 1587-1596.

³⁶Adelman, A. (2000). Determinants of growth and development of the Australian economy. *Australian Journal of Economics*, 14(3): 19-21, 2000.

³⁷ Le Billon, Philippe, and Alejandro Cervantes. "Oil prices, scarcity, and geographies of war." *Annals of the Association of American Geographers* 99, no. 5 (2009): 836-844.

³⁸Kollias, Christos, Catherine Kyrtsov, and Stephanos Papadamou. "The effects of terrorism and war on the oil price-stock index relationship." *Energy Economics* 40 (2013): 743-752.

³⁹Noguera-Santaella, José. "Geopolitics and the oil price." *Economic Modeling* 52 (2016): 301-309.

⁴⁰Corbett, Michael. "Oil Shock of 1973-74." *Federal Reserve History*, 22 (2013).

⁴¹Noguera-Santaella, José. "Geopolitics and the oil price." p. 304.

support for Israel from Portugal, Rhodesia, and South Africa, the embargo was extended to include them as well.⁴²

As a result of the conflict, the major oil producers in the region could not produce for the international market, leading to massive demand in the midst of decreasing supply.⁴³ The conflict affected the posted prices of crude oil, which soared from \$3 per barrel in 1972 to about \$12 USD per barrel in the international market, with the alteration of the supply and demand system of oil in the international oil market.⁴⁴ While the sudden hike in the price of oil was hurting crude oil importers and making global headlines as journalists regarded it as the “first oil shock,”⁴⁵ Barsky and Kiliana present a record of global oil production of only 4.4 million barrels per day, indicative of about 7.5 percent deficit.⁴⁶ This record was almost the same as that of *Foreign Policy*, which recorded a deficit of 7.4%.⁴⁷

Regardless of the cause, and considering the complex nature of conflicts, Nigeria gained from the oil crisis mainly because oil importers’ attention drifted toward alternative sources (Africa) of supply, leading to increased earnings from a mere “\$1billion USD” in the early 1970s to over “\$8billion by 1974.”⁴⁸ Also, it emerged from being a side-line member to the sixth most influential member of OPEC.⁴⁹

Against a massive record of earnings from the sales of crude oil on the international market, the country contradictorily experienced severe petrol shortages on the domestic front in the mid-1970s that raged from 1973 to 1977.⁵⁰ According to the *Daily Times*, the shortage of petrol was very severe, resulting in the downfall of essential socio-economic activities and creating long queues in the filling stations.⁵¹ Following acute shortages in petrol in many Nigerian cities, especially in the Northern part, the government of Nigeria, which was controlled by Northern elements in the military, set up a judicial commission of inquiry to investigate the problems of product scarcity in 1976.⁵² According to available data, two main issues account for the scarcity of petrol in Nigeria during the oil boom.

Explaining the cause of petrol shortages in this period, a participant who was one of the earliest engineers in the Nigerian oil industry noted the following:

⁴²Ibid., p.8.

⁴³Hamilton, James D. "This is what happened to the oil price-macro-economy relationship." *Journal of Monetary Economics*38, no. 2 (1996): 215-220.

⁴⁴ Ibid., 216.

⁴⁵Hamilton, James D. *Historical oil shocks*. No. w16790. National Bureau of Economic Research, 2011 (<https://www.nber.gov/>).

⁴⁶Barsky, Robert B., and Lutz Kilian. "Do we really know that oil caused the great stagflation? A monetary alternative." *NBER Macroeconomics annual* 16 (2001): 137-183.

⁴⁷Oppenheim, V. H. "The past: we pushed them." *Foreign Policy* 25 (1976): 24-57.

⁴⁸ Pinto, Brian. "Nigeria during and after the oil boom: A policy comparison with Indonesia." *The World Bank Economic Review* 1, no. 3 (1987): 419-445. p. 425.

⁴⁹Ibid., 420.

⁵⁰Federal Republic of Nigeria. *Report of the Judicial Commission of Inquiry into the Shortage of Petroleum Products*, Federal Ministry of Information, Lagos, 1976.

⁵¹Adamu, Haroun. 1976. "Long Queues Emerged." *Daily Times* 14 May 1976.

⁵²Federal Republic of Nigeria. *Report of the Judicial Commission of Inquiry into the Shortage of Petroleum Products*, Federal Ministry of Information, Lagos, 1976.

“The problem of fuel scarcity in 1974 was caused by global inflation which led to a massive increase in the price of refined oil. The original suppliers could not supply at a normal and affordable rate. “The government had to take over the downstream sector to regulate the incessant price fluctuations.”⁵³

The global inflationary rate had increased in the period under consideration, as reported by the *Bullion*, a publication of Nigeria’s Central Bank⁵⁴, and the *New York Times*.⁵⁵ In a related work titled “The Great Inflation of the 1970s,” Collard and Dellas provided empirical evidence that the oil price shocks in the 1970s were responsible for higher inflationary figures.⁵⁶ Moreover, the downstream sector in Nigeria before “1971 was not regulated.” Therefore,⁵⁷ market forces were the determinant of prices. If market forces determined prices, then the inflation of the 1970s caused by oil shocks in the international market was directly related to the upsurge in the domestic price of petrol, leading to shortages. Similarly, with an expanded domestic economy accentuated by the oil boom, the only local refinery, which was initially owned by Shell-BP before 1971 (built in 1965), could only cater for approximately 60,000 barrels per day at the maximum production level.⁵⁸ Such a figure was “insignificant,” causing the country to rely on the international market for domestic petrol.”⁵⁹ This suggests that Nigeria’s domestic petrol prices were prone to the fluctuations of international capitalists during the boom era with attendant inflation.

In any case, the volatility challenge has had a significant effect on both the prices of petrol and the attendant implication of shortages in its supply. Following from the above analysis, one central thing can be gleaned. The exogenous views placed the burden of the 1970s’ petrol shortages on geopolitical tensions and the accompanying challenge of inflation, leading to shortages in Nigeria’s domestic economy. The following will discuss the second oil shock to determine if it had a similar impact on petrol distribution in Nigeria.

The Gulf War

In 1990, Saddam Hussein’s armed forces led an invasion of the small country of Kuwait and took over its control for approximately 7 months.⁶⁰ Seeing the repercussions of the conflict as capable of disrupting global oil supply, the United Nations, supported by the United States, organized and intervened.⁶¹ At the time, Iraqi officials maintained that Kuwait had devised a means of stealing its oil using slant drilling

⁵³Interview with Chief Fadeyi (aged 85), on May 16, 2019.

⁵⁴The Central Bank of Nigeria *Annual Report and Statement of Accounts*. Lagos: Central Bank of Nigeria, 1975.

⁵⁵Bohi, D. R. *Energy price shocks and macroeconomic performance*. *New York Times*, February 12, 1974.

⁵⁶ Collard, Fabrice, and Harris Dellas. “The great inflation of the 1970s.” *Journal of money, credit and banking* 39, no. 2-3 (2007): 713-731.

⁵⁷F. R. A. Marinho, *Nigeria’s Petroleum Industry: A Maverick Pioneer*. Lagos: Macmillan Nigeria, 2010.

⁵⁸The Old Port Harcourt Refinery has a maximum capacity of 60,000 barrels per day.

⁵⁹Oriakhi, D. E., and Iyoha Daniel Osaze. “Oil price volatility and its consequences on the growth of the Nigerian economy: An examination (1970-2010).” *Asian economic and financial review* 3, no. 5 (2013): 683.

⁶⁰Musallam and Musallam Ali *Iraqi invasion of Kuwait: Saddam Hussein, his state, and international power politics* British Academic Press, 1996.

⁶¹Freedman, L., & Karsh, E. (1993). *The Gulf conflict, 1990-1991: Diplomacy and war in the new world order*. Princeton University Press, 1993.

techniques.⁶² However, as with most government explanations, it was contested by Kuwait, who rejected such claims as false. This is even more complicated considering that Kuwait was yet to get back the \$14 billion USD it had loaned to Iraq during its disagreement with Iran.⁶³ This is apart from the fact that Iraq was quite displeased with Kuwait's "overproduction of oil to the international market," which had a remarkable repercussion on Iraq's financial position.⁶⁴ The conflict increased oil prices, which moved from \$21 barrels per day in August to \$46 barrels per day by October 1990.⁶⁵ As with the previous sections, our concern in this section is to explain how this high volatility in oil prices led to petrol shortages in Nigeria. As was the case with the first oil shock in the early 1970s, Nigeria gained more from oil exports as other major oil producers were affected by the conflict.⁶⁶ In fact, the report of the *Pius Okigbo Panel of Inquiry*, which was instituted to investigate the windfall of oil proceeds during the Gulf War, revealed that Nigeria gained over \$12 billion.⁶⁷ In one instance, massive reports from international media pressured the Federal Military Government to set up *the Belgore Commission of Inquiry into Fuel Crises* in 1992 and suspended some NNPC staff.⁶⁸ In an attempt to answer the question of what caused petrol shortages during the oil windfall, an insider explained:

"You know the refineries could not satisfy increased demand in the 1990s...and even when the government expanded the capacity of the Kaduna Refinery, demand far outweighs local supply...we relied on the international market for petrol at exorbitant prices." The sacking of some of my junior colleagues during shortage in 1992 was nothing short of window dressing and the government knows."⁶⁹

Challenge of Exchange Rate Fluctuation

This subtheme explains the link between oil price volatility and exchange rate fluctuations and how it has impacted Nigeria's petrol shortages. First, it is significant to note that petrol is traded in US dollars, making it the currency of international oil business, just as the English language is the acceptable language used mostly in oil deals.⁷⁰ Therefore, any small disruption that affects the "perfect feature of the market," such as geopolitical developments as discussed above or forces of demand and supply, has direct consequences on the dollar.⁷¹ Based on market flexibility, economists, including Sari and Soyta, established the nexus

⁶²Gause III, F. Gregory. "Iraq's Decisions to Go to War, 1980 and 1990." *The Middle East Journal* (2002): 47-70.

⁶³ Karsh, Efraim, and Inari Rautsi. "Why Saddam Hussein invaded Kuwait." *Survival* 33, no. 1 (1991): 18-30.

⁶⁴*Ibid.*, 20.

⁶⁵ Verleger, Philip K. "Understanding the 1990 oil crisis." *The Energy Journal* 11, no. 4 (1990): 15-33.

⁶⁶Everhart, S., & Duval-Hernandez, R. *Oil windfall management in Mexico: historical experience and policy options for the future* World Bank, 2001.

⁶⁷Agbese, Pita. "The 'stolen' Okigbo panel report: Of malfeasance and public accountability in Nigeria." *Guyer and Denzer, eds., Vision and Policy* (2005): 55-75.

⁶⁸The Federal Military Government of Nigeria *Belgore Commission of Inquiry into the 1992 Fuel Crisis* Ministry of Information, Abuja.

⁶⁹Interview with Festus Marhino (aged 87) on May 25, 2019.

⁷⁰Falola, Toyin, and Genova, Ann. *The politics of the global oil industry: An Introduction* Greenwood Publishing Group, 2005.

⁷¹Olomola, P. A., and Akintoye V. Adejumo. "Oil price shock and macroeconomic activities in Nigeria." *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics* 3, no. 1 (2006): 28-34.

between the appreciation in the value of the US dollar and lower prices of oil in the international market.⁷² This is largely because dollar appreciation directly increases the pressure on the currencies of oil-producing states, leading to value reduction.⁷³ The observation of economists, which has become an incontestable fact in recent times, also indicates that whenever the dollar-worth increases, it is usually accompanied by “dwindling prices of oil.”⁷⁴ The following explanation tests this position and how the rising dollar in the international market induced Nigeria’s petrol scarcity.

During the oil boom in the 1970s, the value of the Nigerian currency, naira, was slightly higher than that of the US dollar, mainly because of the massive exports of crude oil to the international market, which allowed oil producers to buy more dollars in the international market.⁷⁵ However, when the bubble burst, leading to a drastic decline in the prices of oil from \$41 per barrel to about \$9 per barrel in the middle of the 1980s, it imposed a serious exchange rate crisis on oil producers, including Nigeria.⁷⁶ The dollar rent, on which a classic oil economy, such as Nigeria, is dependent for its economic growth, is no longer obtained, triggering various crises in the rentier economy.⁷⁷ Bullion observed that the dollar, which it needed to maintain the economy and to buy petrol from the international market, was no longer available, with a budget deficit of over ₦17 billion accumulated from 1980 to 1984.⁷⁸ The insufficiency in foreign exchange or the dollar increased the pressure on the local currency, pushing the inflationary rate to over 40 percent by the end of 1984.⁷⁹ By the beginning of 1985, ₦0.8938 naira exchanged for \$1 USD.⁸⁰ However, a year later, when Nigeria’s economy continued to decline as a result of the rising US dollar, especially when dwindling oil prices compelled the Ibrahim Babangida regime to accept the terms of the Structural Adjustment program, the naira plummeted to ₦2.0206 in exchange for \$1.⁸¹ Although the drop in the value of local currency was rampant in the 1980s, it was particularly severe among oil-producing states in Africa, such as Nigeria and Libya, whose leadership has come to embrace oil rents as a means to maintain their power.⁸²

⁷² Sari, Ramazan, Shawkat Hammoudeh, and Ugur Soytaş. "Dynamics of oil price, precious metal prices, and exchange rate." *Energy Economics* 32, no. 2 (2010): 351-362.

⁷³ Ghosh, Sajal. "Examining crude oil price–Exchange rate nexus for India during the period of extreme oil price volatility." *Applied Energy* 88, no. 5 (2011): 1886-1889.

⁷⁴ Davig, Troy, Nida Çakır Melek, Jun Nie, A. Lee Smith, and Didem Tüzemen. "Evaluating a year of oil price volatility." *Federal Reserve Bank of Kansas City, Economic Review* 100, no. 3 (2015): 5-30.

⁷⁵ Coudert, Virginie, Valérie Mignon, and Alexis Penot. "Oil price and the dollar." *Energy Studies Review* 15, no. 2 (2008).

⁷⁶ Jaffe, Amy Myers, and Robert A. Manning. "The shocks of a world of cheap oil." *Foreign Aff.* 79 (2000): 16.

⁷⁷ Pinto, Brian. "Nigeria during and after the oil boom: A policy comparison with Indonesia." *The World Bank Economic Review* 1, no. 3 (1987): 419-445.

⁷⁸The Central Bank of Nigeria “Bullion: Dwindling incomes to Nigeria” Budget analysis for 1985.

⁷⁹Ibid., 34.

⁸⁰Etuk, Ete Harrison. "Forecasting Nigerian naira-us dollar exchange rates by a seasonal arima model." *American Journal of scientific research* 59 (2012): 71-78.

⁸¹Ibid.

⁸² Sandbakken, Camilla. "The limits to democracy posed by oil rentier states: The cases of Algeria, Nigeria and Libya." *Democratization* 13, no. 1 (2006): 135-152.

OPEC and the International Oil Market

In international politics, state actors have designed objectives on which they relate to one another. Although states would always seek to achieve what Morgenthau described as “national interest,”⁸³ they may opt to cooperate with those that share “similar interests.”⁸⁴ This assumption is even more true in an increasingly liberal international system where cooperation is elevated and cherished as “synonymous with development.”⁸⁵ Axelrod and Dion maintained that states tend to benefit more when they cooperate in pursuit of common interests than when they struggle as individuals.⁸⁶ This is especially true when the interests of smaller states collide with those of more powerful states.⁸⁷ Deducing from the above propositions, states are more likely to benefit from cooperation than when they seek to act alone in the pursuit of blatant “self-interest.”⁸⁸ Besides, cooperation becomes easier when the actors are faced with a “common threat.”⁸⁹ The explanation above captured the scenario leading to the emergence of the OPEC, arguably an influential cartel in global politics.⁹⁰ In the following, I explain how it has been able to affect oil prices using its “quota system.”⁹¹ According to Gaul et al., the quota system is based on “a ‘fair’ allocation of share of production that considers factors such as the capacity to produce, population, and reserve.”⁹² But how has these actions compounded the problem of Nigerian petrol shortages?

The 1950s witnessed a steady decline in the global oil market, which affected oil-producing economies due to the dwindling revenue caused by the discovery of new production centers (former USSR and new transnational oil companies).⁹³ The major oil-producing economies realized the negative effect of unchecked systematic decline in oil revenue on tax returns from transnational oil companies, the sole operators on which host countries depended for taxes.⁹⁴ While the prices continued to record a downward trend, the situation worsened with the increased penetration of the already “shrinking market place”⁹⁵ by

⁸³ Morgenthau, Hans J. "What is the national interest of the United States?" *The Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science* 282, no. 1 (1952): 1-7.

⁸⁴Grieco, J. M. *Cooperation among nations: Europe, America, and non-tariff barriers to trade*. Cornell University Press, New York, 1990.

⁸⁵Taylor, Paul, and Arthur John Richard Groom. *Frameworks for international cooperation*. Pinter, 1990.

⁸⁶ Axelrod, Robert, and Douglas Dion. "The further evolution of cooperation." *Science* 242, no. 4884 (1988): 1385-1390.

⁸⁷Axelrod, Robert, and William Donald Hamilton. "The evolution of cooperation." *science* 211, no. 4489 (1981): 1390-1396.

⁸⁸Fearon, James D. "Bargaining, Enforcement, and International Cooperation." *International organization* 52, no. 2 (1998): 269-305.

⁸⁹Kohler, T. A., and Carla R. Van West. "The calculus of self-interest in the development of cooperation: sociopolitical development and risk among the northern Anasazi." In *Evolving complexity and environmental risk in the prehistoric Southwest*, pp. 169-196. CRC Press, 2018.

⁹⁰Adelman, Morris A. "OPEC as a Cartel." *OPEC Behavior and World Oil Prices* (1982): 37-63.

⁹¹Gault, J., Spierer, C., Bertholet, and Bahman Karbassioun. "How does OPEC allocate quotas?" *Journal of Energy Finance & Development* 4, no. 2 (1999): 137-148.

⁹² Gault, John, Bahman Karbassioun, Charles Spierer, and Jean-Luc Bertholet. "OPEC production quotas and their application to non-OPEC countries." *Energy Policy* 18, no. 1 (1990): 73-79.

⁹³Khan, Mehreen. "There are now more than 3bn barrels of excess oil in the world," *The Telegraph*, November 10, 2015.

⁹⁴Danielsen, A. L. *Evolution of OPEC*. Harcourt Brace Jovanovich, 1982.

⁹⁵Tétrault, Mary Ann. *Organization of Arab Petroleum Exporting Countries: History, Policies, and Prospects*. Westport, CT: Greenwood Press, 1981.

new industry players, scrambling for market share. Prior to 1960, the major oil-producing economies of the Middle East commenced meeting to resolve strategic areas of concern regarding the tax mechanism of producing states, benchmarks for oil production, and the greater involvement of producing states in concessions, as stated below:⁹⁶

...direct involvement in exploration and production activities; participation in the equity of existing concessions; progressive and accelerated relinquishing of acreage of existing contract areas; the adoption of industry conservation rules; and the fixing of prices by the governments of member countries."⁹⁷

With the shift in oil industry control from the 'seven sisters' (then the biggest oil transnational corporations)⁹⁸ to its member countries, OPEC assumed the duty of an oil price setter, which altered the structural feature of the global oil industry.

Although other factors made it possible for OPEC to emerge as a prominent cartel capable of influencing oil prices, the desire to gain more from oil sales in the international market propelled member states to increase their participation in the oil economy.⁹⁹ During the oil crisis in the early 1970s, OPEC bypassed oil multinationals and increased the price of oil by the end of 1973, when all measures to persuade the transnationals failed.¹⁰⁰ As a member, Nigeria gained considerably from the oil boom that accompanied OPEC's posted prices quadrupling "revenue between 1970 and 1974."¹⁰¹ While higher prices are generally good for oil producers, the following argues that OPEC moves sometimes affect the downstream sector in countries like Nigeria that use the proceeds of crude to buy petrol from the same international market it sells crude.

Once crude oil prices increase in the international market, the price of petrol would automatically increase because it is a "by-product of crude oil."¹⁰² If the nexus between crude oil and petrol is true and scientifically explained, petrol prices are expected to increase considering the additional cost incurred in "refining and transportation."¹⁰³ Manning applied this logic to estimate an upward push in the prices of refined oil in the UK market between 1982 and 2001.¹⁰⁴ In relation to the specific case of Nigeria in the 1970s when its dependence on the import of petrol for domestic use began, an independent marketer whose family has

⁹⁶Adelman and Morris Albert *The world petroleum market* John Hopkins University Press, 1972.

⁹⁷Danielsen, A. L. *Evolution of OPEC*. p. 12.

⁹⁸Sampson, Anthony. *The Seven Sisters: The Great Oil Companies and the World They Shaped* New York: Viking Press, 1975.

⁹⁹ Griffin, James M. "OPEC behavior: a test of alternative hypotheses." *The American Economic Review* 75, no. 5 (1985): 954-963.

¹⁰⁰Arab light crude from \$3.65 to \$5.119; In December 1973, the Organization of the Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC) raised the posted price of the Arab light further to \$11.651.

¹⁰¹ Freund, Bill. "Oil boom and crisis in contemporary Nigeria." *Review of African Political Economy* 5, no. 13 (1978): 91-100.

¹⁰² Ghosh, Sajal. "Examining crude oil price-Exchange rate nexus for India during the period of extreme oil price volatility." *Applied Energy* 88, no. 5 (2011): 1886-1889. p. 1889.

¹⁰³ Turner, Terisa. "Two refineries: A comparative study of technology transfers to the Nigerian refining industry." *World Development* 5, no. 3 (1977): 235-256.

¹⁰⁴Wlazlowski, Szymon. "Petrol and crude oil prices: asymmetric price transmission." (2001): 1-25.

been in the business of selling petrol observed right from the initial period of nationalization had the following to say:

“Once the price of crude oil increases in the international market, it becomes difficult for us to maintain price stability because we would be running at a loss.” It is understandable that Nigeria would gain from OPEC’s demand for higher pricing, but these gains are swallowed by the higher prices paid for the import of petrol, which is unfortunately imported from outside the country’s shores.”¹⁰⁵

While one can argue that the country has a policy of subsidizing the price of imported oil to cushion the effect of high volatility, industry players observed that the subsidy policy is “fraud with corruption,” compounding the¹⁰⁶ nation’s unfavorable terms of trade.

Nonetheless, OPEC’s pricing policy was adversely affected when non-OPEC oil producers increased their market share of global oil production in the early 1980s. The share of non-OPEC countries’ oil production in the international market rose to approximately 71% by the middle of 1980, from 48% in the 1970s.¹⁰⁷ The taking over of the larger market share by non-OPEC producing states led to price disparity because these new suppliers were not “obliged to respect OPEC pricing rules.”¹⁰⁸

As a result of the oil glut in the second half of the 1980s, OPEC introduced measures that led to massive reductions in member countries’ production quotas to restore the market imbalances that account for the glut.¹⁰⁹ Consequently, Nigeria’s production quota dropped from a high of over 2 million barrels per day in the early 1980s to 1 million barrels per day in 1986, significantly reducing the country’s main source of foreign income and revenue.¹¹⁰ As a result of lower income accrued from the reduction in oil output, Nigeria was unable to pay for petrol subsidies needed to moderate the impact of the international prices for petrol, causing “indignation among its citizens.”¹¹¹ In response to the newly introduced cutbacks, many Nigerians questioned the rationale for Nigeria’s continued membership of the organization.¹¹² Some contended that Nigeria should withdraw from the body, increase its oil production, and lower its prices to raise the resources needed for national development.¹¹³ Among the participants I interviewed, one who held the view that Nigeria should have withdrawn from the body since the 1980s made the following observations:

¹⁰⁵Interview with Alhaji Shafa (aged 64), on May 12, 2019.

¹⁰⁶McPherson, Charles, and Stephen MacSearraigh. "Corruption in the petroleum sector." *The Many Faces of Corruption* (2007): 191.

¹⁰⁷IEA, 2005. *World Energy Outlook: Middle East and North Africa Insights*, 2005

¹⁰⁸ Ramcharran, Harri. "Oil production responses to price changes: an empirical application of the competitive model to OPEC and non-OPEC countries." *Energy economics* 24, no. 2 (2002): 97-106.

¹⁰⁹Gault, J., Spierer, C., Bertholet, and Bahman Karbassioun. "How does OPEC allocate quotas?" *Journal of Energy Finance & Development* 4, no. 2 (1999): 137-148.

¹¹⁰Nwankwo, G. O. "Nigeria and OPEC: To Be or not to be?" *Economic and Financial Review* 20, no. 1 (1982): 6-13.

¹¹¹Ibid., p. 7.

¹¹²Ibid., p. 6-13.

¹¹³Kaufmann, R. K., Andrew Bradford, Laura H. Belanger, John P. McLaughlin, and Yosuke Miki. "Determinants of OPEC production: Implications for OPEC behavior." *Energy Economics* 30, no. 2 (2008): 333-351.

As far as I am concerned, Nigeria should have long withdrawn from that body. It has only reduced Nigeria's production capacity. Other non-OPEC members have done well by allowing market forces to determine oil prices. In short, there is no visible gain for being members of the body."¹¹⁴

This position appeared in Nigeria's newspapers in the mid-1980s with critical voices casting aspersions on Nigeria's continued membership of the body.¹¹⁵ The argument goes that perhaps with greater income, the country would be able to build its own refineries or even expand on the ones built with the proceeds of the 1970s oil boom.¹¹⁶ However, others argued that Nigeria alone would be unable to alter the oil market, specifically citing the period before Nigeria's membership of OPEC.¹¹⁷ However, others focused on the political gains of Nigeria's membership by reinforcing the "improved status" across continental Africa, as one commentator asserted:

"Nigeria's proposed withdrawal from OPEC may in fact reduce it to a puppet's position and make her ludicrous in her new "high horse" position, which will be short-lived and undesirable."¹¹⁸

In response to the oil glut in the mid-1980s, OPEC adopted a more flexible pricing system, which is "market-related," according to Fattouh.¹¹⁹ Going by the new formula, prices are determined by how well OPEC reads the forces of demand and supply to the oil market." However, Kilian maintained that "misinformation or rumor" could also affect OPEC's ability to ascertain the extent of supply to meet the demand for its products.¹²⁰

Moreover, Smith once observed that the bureaucracy in the internal workings of the body can inhibit the most significant objective of price determination. Normally, organizations that involve resourceful members and in which all members have some degree of influence, such as the one under consideration, have the likelihood that decision-making becomes difficult. This was precisely the point made by Smith, who posited the following:

"OPEC acts as a bureaucratic cartel; i.e., a cooperative enterprise weighed down by the cost of forging consensus among members and, therefore, partially impaired in pursuit of the common good."¹²¹

No doubt, the organization has recorded some victories in its quest to increase oil prices, but reaching a consensus for reduction in production has not been without difficulties. When a member's estimates show evidence of less demand in the international market, it usually persuades members to reduce production

¹¹⁴Interview with Musa Ali (aged 75) on May 27, 2019

¹¹⁵Ozoemene, Kanayo. "Stability in world oil market," *New Nigerian*, 5 May 1983. p. 7;

¹¹⁶Akaraogun, Olu. "*New Nigerian*, May 10, 1983." p. 12.

¹¹⁷ Klieman, Kairn A. "US oil companies, the Nigerian civil war, and the origins of opacity in the Nigerian oil industry." *The Journal of American History* 99, no. 1 (2012): 155-165.

¹¹⁸ Fubara, Bedford A. "The ethics of Nigeria's proposed withdrawal from the organization of petroleum exporting countries." *Journal of Business Ethics* 5, no. 4 (1986): 327-332. p. 331.

¹¹⁹Fattouh, Bassam. *OPEC's pricing power: The need for a new perspective* Oxford Institute for Energy Studies, 2007.

¹²⁰Kilian, Lutz. *Oil Price Volatility: Origins and Effects* No. ERS-2010-02. WTO Staff Working Paper, 2010.

¹²¹Smith, James L. "Inscrutable OPEC? Behavioral tests of the cartel hypothesis." *The Energy Journal* (2005): 51-82.

to a agreeable level. This is due to several factors, including market share, member states' challenges, and influence (negotiating power).¹²²

Yet, member states sometimes violate the terms of the agreements reached on production cuts because the organization does not have an agency to ensure compliance.¹²³ Sometimes, other members rely on credible evidence to accuse one another of violating agreements on production cuts. However, the organization did not punish violators but rather to exert pressure against the will of the member states.¹²⁴ The challenge of ensuring compliance among member states on the decision to reduce production increases whenever the scale of reduction is high. This is especially the case with small member states who have always criticized the "pro-rata" template for production cuts. Also, it has proven to be more difficult for countries under recession to agree to cut oil production in compliance with the Organization of the Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC). Recently, Nigeria had to engage OPEC in a series of discussions increasing production against OPEC's general agreement on production cuts.¹²⁵ However, it did not stop the country from experiencing petrol shortages.¹²⁶ This does not invalidate OPEC's role in oil price volatility.

CONCLUSION

In essence, the article explored the volatile nature of the international oil market and how it has compounded the challenge of Nigeria's inadequate supply of petrol. This was done through an examination of three causal factors of oil price volatility, including geopolitical developments, the Organization of the Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC) system of production, and exchange rate fluctuations. The writer finds that these two – geo-political developments and the exchange rate fluctuations, of the factors noted above have directly and indirectly affected the stability of Nigeria's petrol supply, leading to petrol shortages.

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¹²² Doran, Charles F. "OPEC structure and cohesion: exploring the determinants of cartel policy." *The Journal of Politics* 42, no. 1 (1980): 82-101.

¹²³Ghoddusi, Hamed, Masoud Nili, and Mahdi Rastad. "On quota violations of OPEC members." *Energy Economics* 68 (2017): 410-422.

¹²⁴Kohl, W. L. (2002). OPEC behavior, 1998–2001. *The Quarterly Review of Economics and Finance*, 42(2), 209–233.

¹²⁵Kaufmann, R. K., Dees, S., Karadeloglou, and Marcelo Sanchez. "Does OPEC matter? An econometric analysis of oil prices." *The Energy Journal* (2004): 67-90.

¹²⁶Elisha Bala-Gbogbo and Yinka Ibukun Oil-Rich Nigeria Fuel Scarcity Weighs on Buhari's Popularity. <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2018-02-26/oil-rich-nigeria-s-fuel-scarcity-weighs-on-buhari-s-popularity>

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